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“THE BATTLE CRY OF A ONE-MAN LIBRARIAN: A PERSONAL EXPERIENCE”

To many, a library is just a place where book and other sources of information can be found, but for academic institutions, a library is not only that. It is more than just a collection of books and a place where student and researchers alike could find refuge. To the academe, it is a gateway to knowledge, a foundation for academic excellence and most importantly, a great platform for making progress and attainment of the overall development of a person.

Librarians are often met with challenges and herculean tasks of maintaining a library that meets the academic standard of quality. For a one-man librarian like myself, it seems like fighting an unseen battle every day. Being a librarian is not just a profession but a relentless struggle against overwhelming workload. Scarce resources, and the ever-evolving demands of accreditation.

I am a lone librarian in a university campus that needs to pass the evaluation of accrediting bodies like the CHED RQUAT, NQUAT and AACUP in order to ensure the offering of quality education to its students. As a lone librarian, my journey has been filled not only with challenges, but mostly moments of self-doubt. I often asked myself whether I can do all the responsibilities when I am only one librarian in our campus with only a meager staff to assist me.

Managing an entire library alone is not easy. The job is more than just organizing books, but more importantly ensuring academic integrity; allowing individuals to access information, providing research assistance, and meeting national and international standards.

As a lone-librarian, this is my story – a battle of resilience, dedication and commitment to pursue excellence in higher education

THE WEIGHT OF RESPONSIBILITIES

Being the only librarian in a university campus with more than two thousand five hundred students, I have multiple responsibilities. I am not just the custodian of books but at the same time the cataloger, IT support, administrator, and also a research consultant. I wear multiple hats at once that every day I juggle with

countless tasks like sorting and shelving books, assisting students with researches, troubleshooting database access issues, and ensuring compliance with quality academic standards and regulations.

THE DIGITAL REVOLUTION: A DOUBLE-EDGED SWORD

Technology today has transformed libraries, and for a lone librarian like myself, digital integration can be both a blessing and a burden. While online resources and e-books have made information retrieval more accessible, managing these systems alone is an uphill battle.

Accreditation bodies like AACUP now require subscription to research databases like ProQuest, ScienceDirect, and JSTOR. These databases are essential for maintaining a topnotch university library, yet they require technical expertise to set up and maintain access and conduct training sessions to help students and faculty navigate digital resources.

With limited support, I was left to troubleshoot system errors, renew subscriptions, and guide students how to do researches while handling traditional library duties. The fight to keep up with digital advancements is relentless, but I need to push forward, knowing that embracing technology is a key to providing students with the best learning experience.

The Challenge of Compliance: CHED RQUAT, NQUAT and AACUP

One of the most critical and exhausting aspects of my job is the preparation for CHED RQUAT, NQUAT and AACUP accreditation. The library plays a very significant role for the school to pass the evaluation of these accreditation and regulating bodies. As a librarian I must ensure that books collections are updated and aligned with the university's program offerings, provide digital access to research databases and on-line journals to meet modern academic demands: Maintain and present accurate reports showing compliance with library standards and improve facilities and services despite budget constraints.

All these requirements add immense pressure to my already DEMANDING ROLE. On top of that, I also must justify every resource, prove the library's relevance and present data that demonstrate its impact on the students learning. Moreover, I often work long hours even on weekends, to secure that everything is in place. Despite all of these responsibilities and its weight, I continue to maintain a positive attitude towards my work, because I genuinely love it.

FIGHTING FOR RECOGNITION AND SUPPORT

One of the toughest battles I faced was advocating for the library's role in academic success. In many institutions, library development is not a foremost priority. Funding is most often allocated to infrastructure projects, faculty salaries, or administrative expenses, while the library is left with minimal support and rely on library fees only.

In preparing for CHED and AACUP assessments, I have to fight for budget increase, justify book acquisitions, and push for digital resource subscriptions which are required. Many times, I have felt frustrated like my efforts go unnoticed, but I continue to advocate because I believe that a university cannot function

without a strong library. I never stopped to seek and fight for the priorities of the needs of the library. I never get tired to ask.

MOMENTS OF TRIUMPH: WHY I KEEP FIGHTING

Despite the challenges, there are moments that make this battle worth fighting for. I find fulfillment in seeing the joy of a student finding the perfect research material for their thesis and other research work. The gratitude of a professor who has accessed a critical journal article through the library's database; the pride of seeing the university passed an accreditation assessment, knowing that the library played a crucial role in its attainment. These small victories remind me why I continue to fight. I may be alone in this battle, but knowing that I am a part these and the impact of my work extends far beyond the walls of the library, is a reason for me to smile and continue the battle.

THE CRY FOR RECOGNITION BECOMES A VOICE OF CHANGE

My cry is not one of complaint but of resilience, determination and purpose. I fight not for myself but for the students, faculty, and researchers who rely on the library for knowledge and success. And indeed, the battle I fought did not go in vain. My cry did not go unheard. It became a voice of change that paved the way to recognition of the library's needs.

In recent years, the administration has begun to recognize the library's crucial role in academic institutional growth and accreditation. A stronger commitment to support library development is given- allocating more funds for book acquisitions, subscription to digital resources, and even considering additional staff in the library. This changed of attention reflects a flourishing awareness that a well-equipped library is not just a requirement for complaisance but a pedestal of excellence in education.

Nonetheless, this journey has often been on one's own, I am purposeful, knowing that the library remains the heart of the university, and I am its custodian. Now, at long last, that battle cry has been heard.